

Original Research

Organizational Culture, Emotional Intelligence, Employee Performance and Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable in Food Manufacturing Industry

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Abstract

This research delves into the influence of organizational culture and emotional intelligence upon employee performance, both directly and indirectly through the intermediary factor of job satisfaction. The sampling technique in this study uses non-probability sampling with saturation sampling method. Utilizing a descriptive quantitative approach via surveys, the research examined 158 workers in the food processing industry at PT Siradj Badawi Cukup Rupiah (SBCR). Data analysis was carried out utilizing the least squares equation method (SEM-PLS) with the Smart PLS 4 application, revealing a significant and favorable effect of organizational culture, emotional intelligence, and job satisfaction upon employee performance. Furthermore, the research uncovered significant favorable direct and indirect effects among organizational culture, emotional intelligence, job satisfaction, and employee performance. By encompassing all employees of PT Siradj Badawi Cukup Rupiah (SBCR), this research contributes valuable insights into human resource management. It highlights how organizational culture and emotional intelligence can influence employee performance within PT Siradj Badawi Cukup Rupiah (SBCR), and underscores the importance of job satisfaction as a mediating factor for improving employee performance. Therefore, this study concludes that Manufacturing Food Industry companies need to provide equal promotion opportunities to every employee, in resolving disputes between employees can be resolved by discussing, companies can use more accurate employee performance measurement tools and provide assessments to employees objectively.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, employee performance, job satisfaction, organizational culture.

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Introduction

Effective human resources play a pivotal role in shaping an enterprise's competitive edge. They wield considerable influence over a business's trajectory, either propelling it forward or impeding its progress. It is the expectation of every organization that its workforce engages wholeheartedly, leveraging their skills, knowledge, expertise, and time to advance the enterprise's purposes (Huda et al., 2022). The attainment of high performance is indispensable for employees to excel in their roles (Akdere & Egan, 2020). The value ascribed to employee performance, as gauged by the enterprise's comprehension of their contributions and their motivation to fulfill their responsibilities, ultimately underpins the enterprise's sustainable competitive advantage (Arviansyah et al., 2022). Performance serves as a benchmark for evaluating how effectively an individual executes their duties in alignment with organizational expectations (Park & Park, 2019); (Tamunomiebi & Oyibo, 2020); (Azmy, 2023). However, optimizing employee performance is a multifaceted endeavor. (Setiawan et al., 2020) contend that the convergence and embrace of job satisfaction, emotional intelligence, and organizational culture by all employees are pivotal in attaining performance excellence. The significance of employee performance cannot be overstated in fulfilling enterprise purposes and improving overall work result. (Mulyasari, 2019) asserts that employee performance can be assessed through work result, encompassing emotional and mental dispositions such as commitment to present tasks and optimism for future endeavors.

Organizational culture pertains to the foundational principles, philosophies, and beliefs adopted and nurtured by an organization to realize its corporate purposes. It stands as a pivotal factor that can shape performance outcomes. These guiding tenets serve as the framework for the organization's functioning (Winarsih & Hidayat, 2022). Organizational culture mirrors employee attitudes and behaviors, encapsulating the organization's vision and mission, as well as its operational (Nursanti et al., 2023), (Theodora et al., 2023). The cohesion among employees, the emotional connection forged among individuals and the organization, the establishment of social networks, and the delineation of behavioral norms are all influenced by organizational culture, which is perpetuated by habitual daily practices (Junita et al., 2022). As highlighted by (Maulidan et al., 2020; (Arifin, 2022), a thorough comprehension of organizational culture fosters a shared understanding among members, thereby fostering enhanced enterprise performance.

Moreover, emotional intelligence plays a significant role in improving employee performance (Kaur & Sharma, 2019). An individual's professional advancement is intricately linked to their stage of emotional intelligence (Hosain et al., 2021; (Kelvina, 2023)). Emotional intelligence holds particular importance in the recruitment procedure, ensuring alignment among prospective employees and the enterprise's values (Azmy, 2023). Human attitudes and behaviors shaped by emotional intelligence are deemed conducive to organizational effectiveness and are vital for fostering a supportive work environment (Setiawan et al., 2020). Emotional intelligence is recognized as a factor in shaping organizational culture. Leaders characterized by high emotional intelligence not only provide support and guidance to their team members but also foster a culture of positivity, thereby maximizing their contributions to the enterprise's success (Goleman, 2009).

When employees experience satisfaction in their roles, they tend to feel a sense of ease and contentment, which in turn fosters retention and reduces turnover intentions. Contented workers are also prone to exhibit heightened stages of happiness, approach skill, and receptiveness, qualities that are valued by their peers (Dewi & Riana, 2020). Job satisfaction, as revealed by research, denotes an employee's contentment with various facets of their job (Barkhuizen & Gumede, 2021). Dissatisfaction among employees, whether with specific job aspects or with the organization as a whole, can lead to diminished job satisfaction, subsequently effecting performance (Paais & Pattiruhu, 2020). Employee job satisfaction encompasses perceptions related to organizational culture, and the management of emotional intelligence in addressing workplace challenges and events (Paais & Pattiruhu, 2020). Elevated stages of job satisfaction signal potential for performance enhancement, thereby aiding the enterprise in achieving its purposes, comprising heightened overall performance. Hence, the significance of job satisfaction cannot be overstated in augmenting employee performance (Shamaileh et al., 2023).

Emotional intelligence affects job satisfaction, according to previous research (Lestari & Wibawa, 2019). In alignment with this, structural model analysis in the research by (Arviansyah et al., 2022) reveals that the latent variables of emotional intelligence and job satisfaction demonstrate relatively high and favorable estimated coefficients, at 0.64, respectively, with a t-value of 5.28, surpassing the critical value of 1.96. This suggests that job satisfaction has the potential to serve as a moderating factor in the connection among emotional intelligence and employee performance. This significant outcome underscores a favorable association among emotional intelligence and job satisfaction. Contrary to this perspective, (Azmy et al., 2022) assert that job satisfaction does not effect worker performance. Furthermore, outcomes from a separate research carried out by (Ramadhona et al., 2020) suggest that employees' emotional tendencies do not influence their job satisfaction, thereby precluding job satisfaction as a moderating variable in employee performance. These disparate outcomes highlight a research gap concerning variables related to employee job satisfaction. Consequently, researchers aim to explore variables pertinent to the food manufacturing industry, given the absence of prior data upon employee job satisfaction in this context.

Based on the gap in previous research, there are differences in research results associated with the problems in this study. The research also clarifies issues with teamwork, which frequently result from disagreements over the best ways to finish tasks. Then, employees do not have the same promotion opportunities related to their work because of the existence of a close family system, so that only employees who have a close relationship with their superiors will get greater opportunities related to promotion. This has an impact on employee job satisfaction so that employees feel less satisfied and can reduce their performance. The measurement tool used by PT Siradj Badawi Cukup Industry (SBCR) to measure employee performance is Traditional Assessment, where employee superiors assess employees manually. Assessments like this are considered less effective because they have the potential to produce subjective assessments and evaluations. Therefore, this analysis's main goal is to investigate the ways in which organizational culture affects workers' performance, job satisfaction, and emotional intelligence.

Literature Review

Organisational Culture

As per (Robbins & Judge, 2008), organizational culture embodies a set of principles that bind employees together and distinguish them from counterparts in other organizations. When persons align their lifestyles and behaviors with these new philosophies and standards, an organizational culture takes shape, fostering heightened motivation and pride within the group toward achieving shared goals. Organizational culture is shaped in part by characteristics like assertiveness, self-awareness, personality, performance, and team orientation (Edison et al., 2016). Research indicates that job satisfaction among workers is likely to increase when an enterprise fosters a strong organizational culture (Lola Novita et al., 2023). Previous studies underscore the substantial influence of organizational culture upon employee satisfaction stages (Arviansyah et al., 2022), (Lola Novita et al., 2023).

H₁: OC favorably affects JS

Emotional Intelligence

The capacity of an individual to recognize, understand, and incorporate their feelings and ideas in order to effectively control their emotions and thoughts is known as emotional intelligence. There are four key categories of social and interpersonal abilities in this domain: self-management, social awareness, self-awareness, and relationship management (Kritner and Knicki: 2014); (Kartono, 2017). Furthermore, Goleman proposes that human emotional intelligence stems from five key domains: recognizing and managing one's own emotions (through self-awareness), motivating oneself for improvement, discerning others' emotions, and fostering interpersonal connections. Emotional intelligence, also known as the skill to comprehend and govern one's emotions, facilitates proactive decision-making (Nursanti et al., 2023). The aptitude to recognize, regulate, and engage with emotions effectively encompasses understanding others' emotions, self-motivation, and nurturing social bonds (Edward & Purba, 2020). Previous research suggests a favorable connection among emotional intelligence and job satisfaction (Arviansyah et al., 2022), (Ramadhona et al., 2020).

H₂: Emotional Intelligence has a favorable effect upon job satisfaction

Employee Performance

Performance is the result of a defined and precisely calculated process in accordance with a clause or prior agreement. Thus, the theory of performance also known as "*job performance*", is a psychological theory of how a person acts in their workplace to achieve the goals set for them. Employee performance consists of several factors, comprising targets, quality, time, and compliance (Edison et al., 2016). According to previous research, organisational culture greatly affects employee performance. Employee performance assessments of organisational efforts to build a technological culture and adapt to change can help improve employee performance (Lola Novita et al., 2023).

In order to cultivate dependable employees, it is imperative to consider variables such as organizational culture and emotional intelligence to enhance their performance (Edward & Purba, 2020). Previous studies suggest that organizational culture significantly influences employees' work dynamics (Arviansyah et al., 2022), (Louhenapessy & Lindawati, 2022), (Lola Novita et al., 2023). Moreover, there exists a favorable connection among an personal's stage of emotional intelligence and their performance at work, with higher emotional intelligence associated with enhanced employee performance (Edward & Purba, 2020). Consistent with earlier research outcomes (Louhenapessy & Lindawati, 2022), (Arviansyah et al., 2022), (Ramadhona et al., 2020), it is asserted that emotional intelligence exhibits a robust and favorable association with employee performance.

H₃: OC favorably affects EP

H₄: EI has a favorable effect upon EP

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction refers to how satisfied an employee is with their current job position. Based on Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs theory, individuals are believed to have five essential needs: self-actualization, security, social interaction, esteem, and physiological requirements. This framework suggests that employees may aspire to achieve beyond basic necessities. Various factors contribute to job satisfaction, comprising salary, the essence of work, opportunities for advancement, supervision, and connections with colleagues (Gibson et al., 1993); (Edison et al., 2020) . The perception an employee holds of their job and their execution of tasks directly affect their performance. Sustaining high stages of employee satisfaction serves as a means for businesses to enhance their employees' performance (Prabawati & Lukman, 2023); (Theodora et al., 2023). When employees feel content in their roles and have autonomy in their work, they are more inclined to be motivated to excel. Consequently, job satisfaction exhibits a favorable connection with performance and efficacy (Lola Novita et al., 2023), (Arviansyah et al., 2022), (Ramadhona et al., 2020), underscoring its significance in influencing employee performance.

H₅: JS favorably affects EP

A robust organizational culture is closely linked with heightened stages of job satisfaction. When employees are content with the overall enterprise or organizational environment, it favorably influences their satisfaction with their specific roles and their subsequent work outcomes (Paais & Pattiruhu, 2020). Both organizational culture and employee satisfaction are pivotal factors contributing to performance enhancement and professional growth (Edward & Purba, 2020). This underscores the significance of aligning organizational culture and job satisfaction to enable employees to optimize their performance and experience job satisfaction (Arviansyah et al., 2022), (Lola Novita et al., 2023). Additionally, empirical studies suggest that employee performance is substantially and positively impacted by organizational culture as mediated by employee satisfaction (Arviansyah et al., 2022). Additionally, greater emotional intelligence among employees is associated with improved awareness and job satisfaction, with job

satisfaction serving as a mediator. Essentially, higher stages of job satisfaction are linked to employees' satisfaction with their roles and their motivation to engage in tasks related to performance (Arviansyah et al., 2022).

H₆: OC has a favorable effect upon EP mediated by JS

H₇: EI upon EP mediated by JS

The research questions in the following table are used as a medium to obtain research data and then distributed to respondents, namely Food Manufacturing Industry employees.

Table 1. Research Questions

No	Variable	Dimensions	Indicator
1	Job satisfaction	Wages	I am satisfied with the salary I receive while working
		Jobs	My boss gives me the opportunity to continue learning to improve my work, so I feel satisfied.
		Promotion opportunities	I have the same opportunities as others to achieve better positions transparently based on merit.
		Supervisor	My supervisor always helps me when I have difficulties at work.
		Coworkers	My coworkers always support me in carrying out my work
2	Organizational Culture	Self-awareness	I always obey the rules that exist in the company
		Aggressiveness	I always set a work plan so that the results are satisfactory
		Personality	My coworkers and I respect and greet each other when we meet.
		Performance	I always work effectively and efficiently
		Team orientation	I can solve problems in the work team well
3	Emotional Intelligence	Self-awareness	I am able to recognize my own emotions and their impact on my decision-making.
		Self-management	I am able to manage and control my emotions in any situation.
		Social awareness	I am able to adapt myself to the goals of the group or organization
		Relationship management	I appreciate criticism with an open mind and accept it when it is justified.

No	Variable	Dimensions	Indicator
4	Employee performance	Target	I always work based on targets that must be met.
		Quality	The quality I produce is in accordance with company standards
		Time	I complete my targets on time
		Follow the principle	I work in accordance with the operational standards set by the company.

Objectives and Research Methodology

The following figure 1. can be used to explain the above hypothesis and is used to illustrate the variables of organisational culture, emotional intelligence that have an effect upon employee performance and job satisfaction:

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

The purpose of this study was to explore the impact of OC, EI to EP by using variables intervening JS. This descriptive quantitative research collected data from employees of PT Siradj Badawi Cukup Rupiah (SBCR). The data obtained in this study is based on questionnaires and in-depth interviews related to several cases. The research centers upon the examination of organizational culture, emotional intelligence, job satisfaction, and employee performance (designated as X1, X2, Z, & Y, respectively). Quantitative data was utilized in this research, as information was gathered, analyzed, and presented in numerical form. The sampling technique in this study uses non-probability sampling with saturation sampling method. A saturated sample of 158 employees from PT SBCR was utilized for the research. The statistical analysis utilized for data proceduring was Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), which employs path analysis with latent variables. Smart Applications PLS 4.

Results and discussion

Table 2. Respondent demographics

Category	Description	Total	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	135 people	85%
	Female	23 people	15 %
Age	21 - 30 Years	45 people	28 %
	31 - 40 Years	42 people	27 %
	41 - 50 Years	69 people	44 %
	≥ 51 Year	2 people	1 %
Education	High School	127 people	80 %
	D3	10 people	6 %
	S1	21 people	14 %

Source: employee data of PT Siradj Badawi Cukup Rupiah (2024)

Table 2 in the descriptive analysis presents the demographic characteristics of each respondent, comprising gender, age, and highest stage of education attained, as part of the research data collection procedure. All respondents are employees of PT Siradj Badawi Cukup Rupiah (SBCR), with the majority being male (135 persons) and female (23 persons). The predominant age group among respondents falls among 41 and 50 years old. Regarding educational attainment, 127 respondents hold a high school diploma, 21 have gotten a bachelor's degree, and 10 possess a diploma.

Measurement Model Analysis (Outer Model)

The purpose of measurement model analysis, also known as the outer model, is to ascertain the validity and reliability of the indicators used to measure latent variables.

Validity Test

Concept discriminant validity demonstrates the extent to which the concept differs from other constructs (unique constructs). Research validity indicates that the research measurement tool is appropriate for the data being calculated.

Table 3. Validity testing based upon loading factor

	EI	EP	JS	OC
EI1	0.775			
EI2	0.825			
EI3	0.834			
EI4	0.848			
EP1		0.838		
EP2		0.820		
EP3		0.843		
EP4		0.826		
JS1			0.811	
JS2			0.819	

	EI	EP	JS	OC
JS3			0.834	
JS4			0.817	
JS5			0.809	
OC1				0.817
OC2				0.827
OC3				0.801
OC4				0.794
OC5				0.791

Table 3. illustrates the utilization of outer loading values to ascertain the feasibility of a structure. In this research, construct values exceeding 0.70 serve as the benchmark. The outer loading values of the indicators utilized surpass the 0.70 threshold. This signifies that each indicator or question pertaining to the variables addressed in the questionnaire meets the requisite discriminant validity criteria. An AVE value exceeding 0.5 is deemed indicative of a valid indicator.

Table 4. Validity testing based upon Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

AVE		
EI	0.674	Valid
EP	0.692	Valid
JS	0.669	Valid
OC	0.650	Valid

The outcomes indicated that the Emotional Intelligence, Employee Performance, Job Satisfaction, and Organizational Culture variables each had an Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value of more than 0.5. This is indicated in table 4. Therefore, the relevant variables are declared valid and meet the test validity criteria.

The outer loading value from the data proceduring outcomes can be proven in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Validity testing based on loading factor

Reliability Test

To evaluate the indicators of the constructs or variables used in the research, reliability testing is done. This process assesses the measurement device's accuracy and consistency. The Reliability of the instrument in obtaining measurements indicates its accuracy and Reliability. Two commonly utilized measures to assess PLS Reliability are composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha. Cronbach's Alpha provides the highest lower bound dependency, whereas composite Reliability represents the true dependency value. Typically, both values are expected to exceed 0.6.

Table 5. Reliability testing based upon Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability

CA		CR	Conclusion
EI	0.838	0.892	Reliable
EP	0.852	0.900	Reliable
JS	0.876	0.910	Reliable
OC	0.865	0.903	Reliable

From the Reliability test outcomes in table 5: above, it can be proven that the Composite Reliability exceeds 0.60. Therefore, this research variable is reliable. The data type structure used in the questionnaire has consistent values.

Table 6. Collinearity statistics

(VIF)	
EI1	1.558
EI2	1.914
EI3	2.041
EI4	2.069
EP1	1.955
EP2	1.842
EP3	2.007
EP4	1.890
JS1	2.008
JS2	2.056
JS3	2.188
JS4	2.039
JS5	1.968
OC1	2.160
OC2	2.104
OC3	1.925
OC4	1.882
OC5	1.987

Table 6: Statistical collinearity (VIF) values are less than 10. Consequently, it can be summarized that the multicollinearity assumption test is not included in this data. Furthermore, to analyse the structural model, the value can be known from the outcomes of R^2 and F^2 .

Structural Model Analysis (Inner Model)

R-Square

(Juliandi, 2018), the R value² can be used to evaluate model robustness. A value of 0.75 indicates a strong model, 0.50 indicates a medium model, and 0.25 indicates a weak model.

Table 7. R-square

	R^2	R^2 adjusted
EP	0.808	0.804
JS	0.821	0.818

Table 7: The obtained outcomes reveal an R^2 value of 0.808 for Employee Performance, indicating a robust model classification (strong). This suggests that the variables of Organizational Culture and Emotional Intelligence can account for 80.8% of the variability in Employee Performance, with the remaining 19.2% attributed to factors beyond the scope of the research variables. Additionally, the R-Square value for Job Satisfaction stands at 0.821, signifying a substantial model classification (strong). This indicates that Organizational Culture and Emotional Intelligence variables can elucidate 82.1% of the variance in Job Satisfaction, leaving 17.9% of the variability unexplained by the research variables.

F-Square

(Juliandi, 2018) an F-Square value of 0.02 indicates a small effect upon internal variables; a value of 0.15 = a smaller effect; and a value of 0.35 = a significant effect.

Table 8. F-square

	EP	JS
EI	0.092	0.203
JS	0.040	
OC	0.120	0.258

According to Table 8, the F-Square values indicate that the endogenous and exogenous variables do not significantly affect each other. Specifically, the F-Square value for the emotional intelligence variable is 0.092. Moreover, the F-Square value of 0.40 suggests that the Job Satisfaction variable has a minimal effect upon the Employee Performance variable. Similarly, the F-Square value of 0.120 indicates that the Organizational Culture variable has a negligible effect on the Employee Performance variable. In contrast, the F-Square value of 0.203 reveals that the Emotional Intelligence variable exerts a relatively moderate effect on the Job Satisfaction variable. Lastly, the F-Square value of 0.258

suggests that the Organizational Culture variable has a moderate influence upon the Job Satisfaction variable.

Effect Significance Test (Bootstrapping)

As per (Ghozali, 2014), the outcomes of bootstrapping analysis shed light upon the significance of each metric in shaping organizational culture, emotional intelligence, employee performance, and job satisfaction. The bootstrapping test outcomes unveil the outcomes of hypothesis testing, delineating both direct and indirect effects. Table 9 Path Coefficients and Table 10 Indirect Effect, presented below, elucidate the outcomes of data analysis carried out utilizing the Smart PLS 4 application.

Direct Effect

The path coefficient and p-value will be utilized to examine the direct effect hypothesis. A favorable path coefficient signifies a unidirectional effect among two variables, whereas a negative path coefficient indicates a bidirectional effect among them. Subsequently, the significance or probability value is computed. According to (Juliandi, 2018), a p-value is deemed significant if it is below 0.05.

Table 9. Path coefficients

Hypothesis	(O)	Std. Dev	T stat	P values	Conclusions
OC -> JS	0.493	0.067	7.327	0.000	Accepted
EI -> JS	0.437	0.067	6.494	0.000	Accepted
OC -> EP	0.390	0.100	3.916	0.000	Accepted
JS -> EP	0.208	0.082	2.539	0.011	Accepted
OC -> EP	0.390	0.100	3.916	0.000	Accepted

Indirect Effect

The direct effect hypothesis will be assessed utilizing the path coefficient and p-value. A favorable path coefficient indicates that the values of the two variables change in tandem: as one value increases or decreases, the other also follows suit. Conversely, a negative path coefficient suggests an inverse connection among the variables, where changes in one variable influence changes in the other. Subsequently, the significance or probability value is computed. According to (Juliandi, 2018), a p-value is considered significant if it is less than 0.05 and not greater than 0.05.

Table 10. Indirect effects

Hypothesis	(O)	Std. Dev	T stat	P values	Conclusions
OC -> JS -> EP	0.103	0.046	2.226	0.026	Accepted
EI -> JS -> EP	0.091	0.036	2.499	0.013	Accepted

Discussion

OC and JS

With a computed T-value of 7.327, surpassing the critical T-value of 1.96, and a significance value of 0.000, the data indicates that organizational culture significantly influences job satisfaction in the workplace. This underscores that the organizational culture at PT Siradj Badawi Cukup Rupiah (SBCR) effects job satisfaction. Consequently, there exists a favorable connection among the stage of employee satisfaction and the robustness of the enterprise's organizational culture.

Given the enterprise's operations in the production sector, where work procedures are closely linked to production equipment, requiring meticulous operation and attention to detail, employees perceive their roles as crucial to the smooth functioning of the enterprise's production procedures. They understand that errors or hazards associated with operating production tools can disrupt or halt operations. As a outcome, employees derive greater satisfaction and confidence in their roles. Previous studies, such as that by (Jufrizen et al., 2023) upon PT Pelabuhan Indonesia (Persero), have also found that organizational culture influences job satisfaction. Similarly, research by (Azhari et al., 2024) looks at how worker satisfaction in oil and gas companies is affected by a good and important organizational culture. Additionally, (Korda & Rachmawati, 2022) determined that organizational culture influences employee satisfaction.

EI and JS

The statistical analysis reveals that emotional intelligence significantly influences job satisfaction, as evidenced by a calculated T-value of 6.494, surpassing the critical T-value of 1.96, with a significance value of 0.000. This research establishes a favorable connection among emotional intelligence and job satisfaction among employees at PT Siradj Badawi Cukup Rupiah (SBCR). It underscores that employees within the organization exhibit high stages of job satisfaction.

The cultivation of employee satisfaction and the overall performance of an organization are significantly influenced by emotional intelligence, as highlighted by (Al-hamami et al., 2015). This is attributed to employees' adeptness at managing their emotions towards their colleagues, which in turn effects their job satisfaction. When employees can effectively regulate their emotions, they feel empowered to demonstrate their capability to complete tasks punctually and contentedly to their superiors. Consequently, they experience reduced stress and insecurity while working, enabling them to maintain focus and perform their duties to the best of their abilities. Additionally, the collaborative atmosphere fostered by employees helping each other enhances job satisfaction. Previous research, such as that carried out by (Alsughayir, 2021), reinforces the favorable and significant connection among emotional intelligence and job satisfaction. Similarly, studies by (Al-hamami et al., 2015), (Ides & Yohana, 2024), and (Abebe & Singh, 2023) corroborate the notion that emotional intelligence is favorable correlated with job satisfaction.

OC and EP

The outcomes of the statistical examination reveal a significant effect of organizational culture upon employee performance. With a calculated T-value of 3.916 surpassing the critical T-value of 1.96, and a significance stage of 0.000, it is evident that organizational culture plays a pivotal role in shaping the performance of employees at PT Siradj Badawi Cukup Rupiah (SBCR). This underscores the notion that a conducive work culture is conducive to employee success.

Organizational culture encompasses the beliefs, principles, and norms embraced by every member of the organization. It serves as a guiding framework in enterprise operations, aiding in problem management and resolution. A robust organizational culture is crucial for improving organizational performance, particularly in fostering sustained improvements in employee performance over the short and long term. These outcomes align with previous research that underscores the significant effect of a favorable organizational culture upon employee performance, as evidenced by studies carried out by (Bagis et al., 2021) and (Setiawan et al., 2020). The present research further bolsters these outcomes, as observed in the research by (Korda & Rachmawati, 2022), highlighting the substantial influence of organizational culture upon employee performance, as also emphasized by (Ides & Yohana, 2024).

EI and EP

At PT Siradj Badawi Cukup Rupiah (SBCR), research indicates that emotional intelligence significantly and favorably affects employee performance. Statistical analysis reveals a calculated T-value of 3.358, surpassing the critical T-table value of 1.96, with a significant value of 0.001. Employees at PT Siradj Badawi Cukup Rupiah (SBCR) actively manage their emotions to foster better and more harmonious connections with their colleagues.

Maintaining a balance among emotion and rationality is paramount. Every decision made by employees is influenced by their emotional intelligence: persons with high emotional intelligence tend to exhibit greater optimism owing to their capability to comprehend, regulate, and influence their own emotions. These outcomes corroborate previous research. For instance, a research on emotional intelligence carried out by (Ides & Yohana, 2024) found a favorable and significant connection among emotional intelligence and employee performance. Additionally, research by (Naz et al., 2019) revealed that emotional intelligence has a favorable and significant effect upon employee performance.

JS and EP

The statistical analysis indicates that job satisfaction significantly influences employee performance, as evidenced by a calculated T-value of 2.539, exceeding the T-value of 1.96, with a significance stage of 0.011. This research underscores the favorable and significant effect of job satisfaction upon the employee performance (EP) at PT Siradj Badawi Cukup Rupiah (SBCR).

The researcher's analysis suggests that this phenomenon stems from employees' performance behavior being driven by their job satisfaction and their belief that they deserve such satisfaction, as evaluated against the established standards at PT Siradj Badawi Cukup Rupiah (SBCR). Previous research by (Fidyah, 2020) has highlighted a favorable connection among employee satisfaction and their performance at work, which aligns with the outcomes of (Egenius et al., 2020). Moreover, studies carried out by (Ides & Yohana, 2024) and (Setiawan et al., 2020) have similarly established the influence of job satisfaction upon employee performance.

OC, JS and EP

The statistical test outcomes indicate that the calculated T value is 2.226 greater than the T table 1.96, and the significant value is 0.026. The outcomes indicate that job satisfaction can control how organisational culture affects the work done by employees.

Research outcomes indicate that job satisfaction is very important to control how organizational culture affects employee performance. Job satisfaction helps make the connection between organizational culture and the way employees perform their jobs. A favorable organizational culture can shape how employees engage with their work, ultimately effecting their performance. Thus far, the organizational culture at PT Siradj Badawi Cukup Rupiah (SBCR) has been instrumental in enabling employees to achieve optimal outcomes and derive satisfaction from their roles. In an environment where employees are satisfied with their jobs, work outcomes tend to improve, underscoring the importance of a supportive organizational culture. The stage of employee satisfaction is closely tied to the robust and meaningful connection with organizational culture (Sugiono & Ardiansyah, 2021), which indirectly influences employee performance. This aligns with the outcomes of (Wua et al., 2022), suggesting that job satisfaction acts as a mediator. When organizational culture prioritizes employee satisfaction as a means to enhance performance, it yields significant favorable effects. Similar conclusions were drawn by (Bagis et al., 2021) and (Korda & Rachmawati, 2022), highlighting the moderating role of job satisfaction among organizational culture and employee performance.

EI, JS and EP

Based on the aforementioned data, the outcomes of the statistical test reveal a T-count value of 2.499, surpassing the critical T-table value of 1.96, with a significant p-value of 0.013. These results indicate that there is a relationship between emotional intelligence and employee performance mediated by job satisfaction. Despite the research hypothesis, self-awareness, social skills, empathy, and care for others the elements that make up emotional intelligence do not have a direct impact on performance. Furthermore, a notable stage of job satisfaction implies an absence of a significant connection among emotional intelligence and employee performance. This contradicts earlier research (Sugiono & Nurhasanah, 2022), which found a favorable association among emotional intelligence, employee performance, and job satisfaction. Similarly, another research (Kelvin & Muchsinati, 2023) reported a favorable connection among these variables.

Conclusion

This research focuses on PT Siradj Badawi Cukup Rupiah (SBCR), and how organizational culture and emotional intelligence affect employees' job satisfaction and their performance. The key outcomes of the research are as follows: Firstly, emotional intelligence emerged as a significant factor effecting employee performance. Secondly, it was observed that emotional intelligence greatly affects employee satisfaction. Thirdly, the research revealed a noteworthy connection among employee satisfaction stages and their performance. Fourthly, organizational culture emerged as a crucial determinant affecting employee performance. Furthermore, the research demonstrated that job satisfaction is significantly influenced by organizational culture, not only directly but also indirectly, as it acts as a mediator among organizational culture and employee performance. A favorable organizational culture contributes to improved employee satisfaction. Lastly, the research emphasized the influence of emotional intelligence upon employee performance within the food proceduring industry, mediated by job satisfaction. Satisfied employees, coupled with a conducive work culture and emotional intelligence, are likely to enhance performance and contribute to achieving enterprise purposes. It was also highlighted that organizational culture and emotional intelligence are influenced by job satisfaction, serving as moderating variables.

This study has limitations including: First, the sample used in this study was only obtained within the scope of one company. Second, the limited number of samples. Meanwhile, the researchers' recommendations for future researchers are: First, expand the scope of observation because this research only focuses on employees in one company. Second, increase the number of respondents to get more accurate results. The research findings have implications, showing that organizational culture and employee emotional intelligence can increase job satisfaction which in turn will have an impact on improving employee performance. Recommendations based on the findings in this study, companies can provide equal promotion opportunities to employees so that they can provide employee job satisfaction to have better performance, promotion opportunities provide opportunities for companies to be able to provide employee opportunities as company development. Then, disagreements in work can be resolved by discussing teamwork issues that often have disagreements, not making differences of opinion personal, and employees focus on optimal work results. Furthermore, companies can use more accurate employee performance measurement tools and provide assessments to employees objectively.

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